

Supplement of

Lidar observations of cirrus cloud properties with CALIPSO from mid-latitudes towards high-latitudes

Qiang Li and Silke Groß

Correspondence to: Qiang Li (qiang.li@dlr.de)

The copyright of individual parts of the supplement might differ from the article licence.

Figure S1. Map of the research area of midlatitudes (35–60°N; 30°W–30°E) and high-latitudes (60–80°N; 30°W–30°E).

Figure S2. Altitude ranges of cirrus cloud formation restricted with the occurrence rate > 1% alongside the altitudes with the maximum occurrence rate indicated with circles in different years (2014 and 2018–2021) and the composite mean values from all 5 years combined. The panels (a–d) show the results in different seasons, respectively.

Figure S3. Box plot representations of the extinction coefficients of ice crystals within cirrus clouds observed with CALIPSO in different seasons in years of 2014 and 2018–2021 as well as the composite results in the 5 years (in panels a, b, e, and f). The results in the high-latitude regions are shown in red and midlatitude in black. Boxes represent the 25th–75th percentiles (from bottom to top). Solid lines through the corresponding boxes stand for the medians and circles for means. Whiskers indicate the 5th and 95th percentiles, and outliers with values falling within the largest 5% and smallest 5% of the distributions of extinction coefficients are not shown here. Considering the occurrence of polar day and polar night in summer and winter, respectively, we also indicate the results only from the day-time measurements in the summer months and from the night-time measurements in the winter months for a fair comparison in different latitudes (in panels c and g).

Figure S4. Histograms of cloud optical depth of cirrus within different latitude domain in summer (JJA: Jun-Jul-Aug) in years of 2014 and 2018–2021 as well as in all 5 years combined. The results derived from the measurements at HL and ML are shown in gray and black, respectively.

Figure S5. Same as Figure S4, but for autumn (SON: Sep-Oct-Nov).

Figure S6. Same as Figure S4, but for winter (DJF: Dec-Jan-Feb).

Figure S7. Box plot representations of the composite distributions of particle linear depolarization ratios (PLDR) of cirrus clouds in each 5-degree latitude bin from 35–80°N in summer in years of 2014 and 2018–2021 as well as in all 5 years combined. Boxes represent the 25th–75th percentiles of the PLDR distributions (from bottom to top). Solid lines through the corresponding boxes stand for the medians and circles for the means. Whiskers indicate the 5th and 95th percentiles, and outliers with values falling within the largest 5% and the smallest 5% of the PLDR distributions are not shown here.

Figure S8. Same as Figure S7, but for autumn.

Figure S9. Same as Figure S7, but for winter.

Figure S10. Comparison of temperatures inside cirrus clouds within different latitude domain in summer. The histograms at HL are shown in gray and at ML in black with the medians indicated in the inset.

Figure S11. Same as Figure S10, but for autumn.

Figure S12. Same as Figure S10, but for winter.